

Original Research

Identification of Stress-Responsive Transcription Factors Interacting with Cysteine Desulfurase through Co-expression Network Analysis under Drought, Heat, and Salinity Conditions in Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*)

Firat Kurt¹, Ertugrul Filiz^{2,*}

Abstract

Cysteine desulfurases are essential enzymes involved in sulfur metabolism, redox regulation, and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) signalling, especially under abiotic stress conditions. This study aimed to explore the gene networks associated with a cysteine desulfurase gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*) in *Solanum tuberosum* exposed to drought, heat, and salinity. A subset of RNA-Seq data (*SRA029323*) were analysed using the Tuxedo pipeline on the Galaxy platform, and $\log_2(FC)$ values were used to assess gene co-expression. A total of 2,397 genes showed strong positive correlation ($r \geq 0.90$) with the target gene, including 201 transcription factors and kinases identified from the iTAK database. Functional annotation revealed that the top co-expressed genes are involved in oxidative stress response, signal transduction, and mitochondrial respiration. Notably, a cytochrome-c oxidase involved in proton transport and copper binding (*PGSC0003DMT400080385*) and a putative membrane protein (*PGSC0003DMT400065426*) were highly upregulated under drought and heat stress, suggesting their role in stress adaptation. Conversely, some uncharacterized genes (e.g., *PGSC0003DMT400096412* and *PGSC0003DMT400022675*) were strongly downregulated under salinity and drought. Network analysis positioned the cysteine desulfurase gene as a central hub linking multiple stress-responsive TF and kinase families, including AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bHLH. These findings contribute to a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms behind abiotic stress responses in potato and may guide future breeding or genetic engineering strategies aimed at improving stress resilience in crops.

Keywords

Mycoprotein, *Lentinus squarrosulus*, Solid-state fermentation, proximate analysis, amino acids.

1 Mus Alparslan University, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Department of Plant Production and Technologies, Mus, Turkey

2 Duzce University, Cilimli Vocational School, Cilimli, Turkey

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: ertugrulfiliz@gmail.com, firat.kurt.usa@gmail.com

Citation: Kurt, F., Filiz, E. (2025). Identification of Stress-Responsive Transcription Factors Interacting with Cysteine Desulfurase through Co-expression Network Analysis under Drought, Heat, and Salinity Conditions in Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*). *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 20.05.2025 / **Accepted:** 24.09.2025 / **Published:** 12.12.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.22736>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Identifikacija transkripcijskih faktorjev, ki se odzivajo na stres in sodelujejo s cisteinsko desulfurazo preko analize mreže soizražanja v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti pri krompirju (*Solanum tuberosum*)

Izvleček

Cisteinska desulfuraza je pomemben encim, ki sodeluje v presnovi žvepla, regulaciji redoks potenciala in signalizaciji vodikovega sulfida (H₂S), zlasti v pogojih abiotičnega stresa. Namen te študije je bil raziskati genetske mreže, povezane z genom *cisteinske desulfuraze* (PGSC0003DMT400078713) v *Solanum tuberosum*, izpostavljenem suši, vročini in slanosti. Analizirana je bila podmnožica podatkov RNA-Seq (SRA029323) z uporabo protokola Tuxedo na platformi Galaxy, vrednosti log₂(FC) pa so bile uporabljene za oceno soekspresije genov. 2397 genov je pokazalo močno pozitivno korelacijo ($r \geq 0,90$) s ciljnim genom, vključno z 201 transkripcijskimi faktorji in kinazami, identificiranimi iz baze podatkov iTAK. Funkcionalna opomba je pokazala, da so geni z najvišjo soekspresijo vključeni v odziv na oksidativni stres, signalno transdukcijo in mitohondrijsko dihanje. Zlasti *citokrom-c oksidaza*, vključena v transport protonov in vezavo bakra (PGSC0003DMT400080385) ter domnevni membranski protein (PGSC0003DMT400065426) so bili močno povečano ekspresijo v suši in toplotnem stresu, kar kaže na njuno vlogo pri prilagajanju na stres. Nasprotno pa so bili nekateri neznaki geni (npr. PGSC0003DMT400096412 in PGSC0003DMT400022675) močno zmanjšani v slanosti in suši. Mrežna analiza je gen *cistein desulfuraza* umestila kot osrednji vozlišče, ki povezuje več družin TF in kinaz, ki se odzivajo na stres, vključno z AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC in bHLH. Ti izsledki prispevajo k boljšemu razumevanju molekularnih mehanizmov, ki stojijo za odzivi na abiotični stres pri *krompirju*, in lahko usmerjajo prihodnje strategije vzreje ali genske tehnologije, namenjene izboljšanju odpornosti pridelkov na stres.

Ključne besede

abiotični stres, ekspresija genov, analiza koekspresije, bioinformatika, presnova žvepla

Introduction

Cysteine desulfurases (CDs), a class of pyridoxal 5'-phosphate (PLP)-dependent enzymes, are indispensable for sulfur metabolism across all organisms. These enzymes catalyse the desulfuration of *L*-cysteine, breaking the carbon-sulfur bond to form a persulfide (-SSH) on a conserved cysteine and releasing alanine (Caubrière et al., 2023). In plants, *cysteine* serves dual roles: as a proteinogenic amino acid and as a precursor for critical biomolecules such as glutathione (GSH), methionine, vitamins (e.g., *biotin*, *thiamine*), and cofactors such as *Fe-S* clusters, *molybdenum cofactor* (Moco) and *S-adenosylmethionine* (Gotor et al., 2015; Tian et al., 2024; Vojtovič et al., 2021). This highlights the key role of *cysteine desulfurases* in plant growth and stress response.

Plant *cysteine desulfurases*, such as mitochondrial *AtNFS1* and chloroplast-localised *AtNFS2/SUFS*, are pivotal for *Fe-S* cluster biosynthesis, a process essential for electron transport, photosynthesis, and DNA repair (Caubrière

et al., 2023). These enzymes transfer sulfur from cysteine to scaffold proteins (e.g., *SUFBC2D*) in coordination with sulfur-relay regulators like *SUFE*. *Cysteine desulfurases*, including *ABA3*, are also involved in *Moco* sulfuration, an essential cytosolic step needed to activate enzymes such as *nitrate reductase* (Caubrière et al., 2023). These enzymes also produce H₂S, a gas that acts as a signalling molecule during stress. For instance, *DES1* (*At5g28030*), a cytosolic enzyme, breaks down *cysteine* into H₂S, *pyruvate*, and *ammonia*, helping to regulate redox balance and autophagy (Jia et al., 2016; Z. Liu et al., 2024). Mitochondrial *β-cyanoalanine synthase* (CAS-C1) also generates H₂S during cyanide detoxification, while *O-acetylserine(thiol) lyase* (OASTL) both synthesises and degrades *cysteine*, maintaining balance across different cell compartments (Khan et al., 2022; Z. Liu et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2022).

The regulatory interplay between *cysteine* synthesis and degradation is governed by the *cysteine synthase complex*, a hetero-oligomer of *serine acetyltransferase* (SAT) and

OASTL, which fine-tunes *cysteine* production in response to sulfur availability (Romero et al., 2014; H. Liu & Xue, 2021). However, certain *OASTL* family members, such as *DES1*, preferentially degrade *cysteine*, highlighting a dynamic equilibrium between anabolic and catabolic pathways (Z. Liu et al., 2024). The resultant H_2S mediates *persulfidation* (*S-sulfhydration*), a post-translational modification that alters protein function by turning $-SH$ groups into $-SSH$ (Aroca et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022). This affects many pathways like the *TCA cycle*, *glycolysis*, and *autophagy*, and works with *ABA signalling* to control stomatal closure and stress tolerance (Khan et al., 2022; Vojtovič et al., 2021).

Cysteine degradation products further influence plant metabolism: *pyruvate* fuels respiration, *ammonia* is assimilated into nitrogen metabolism, and H_2S enhances tolerance to abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and heavy metal toxicity (Tian et al., 2024; Z. Liu et al., 2024). Compartmentalisation of these processes—via cytosolic *DES1*, mitochondrial *CAS-C1*, and chloroplast NFS-like enzymes—ensures spatial regulation of sulfur flux (Yang et al., 2022; Caubrière et al., 2023). Despite these advances, how *cysteine desulfurase* activity, H_2S signalling, and stress adaptation are connected is still not fully understood.

This study aims to understand how *cysteine desulfurase* interacts with other genes in *Solanum tuberosum* (potato) under drought, heat, and salinity stress conditions. The main focus is to find transcription factors and kinases that may take part in these stress-related gene networks. By combining RNA-Seq-based co-expression analysis with information about the functions of regulatory proteins, it aims to uncover molecular pathways linked to *cysteine desulfurases*. Since *cysteine desulfurases* play key roles in sulfur metabolism, redox balance, and hydrogen sulfide signalling, it is important to learn which genes they work with during stress. This knowledge can help us find important regulatory points that support stress adaptation in potato. These insights could support breeding or genetic engineering efforts to improve stress tolerance in potatoes.

Materials and Methods

This study used RNA-Seq expression data generated by the Potato Genome Sequencing Consortium (PGSC) for the reference genotype DM1-3 Phureja (Xu et al., 2011; Massa et al., 2011). The raw sequencing data were retrieved from the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession

SRA029323, associated with BioProject PRJEB2430. From this comprehensive dataset, only the expression data corresponding specifically to abiotic stress conditions—heat (35 °C), salinity (150 mM NaCl), and drought (260 μ M mannitol)—were selected for analysis.

RNA-Seq Data Processing and Expression Analysis

At the time of analysis, the subset of RNA-Seq data was processed using the Tuxedo protocol (Trapnell et al., 2012), which was then available as a predefined workflow on the Galaxy platform (Afgan et al., 2016). Although this exact pipeline is no longer present on current versions of Galaxy, all steps were documented and consistently applied to the dataset.

Raw sequencing reads in FASTQ format were aligned to the *Solanum tuberosum* reference genome (version 4.03, from Phytozome v12.1) using TopHat (Trapnell et al., 2009). TopHat is a splice-aware aligner that first detects potential exon-exon junctions and then maps the reads using Bowtie (Langmead et al., 2009). The output consisted of sorted and indexed BAM files showing the genomic locations of aligned reads.

The aligned reads were then used in Cufflinks (Trapnell et al., 2010) for reference-guided transcript assembly and expression quantification. To enable comparison across samples, transcript assemblies were merged using Cuffmerge, and Cuffcompare was used to match assembled transcripts with the reference annotation. Although differential expression analysis was performed using Cuffdiff, this study did not rely on its p-value outputs for filtering. Instead, the $\log_2(\text{Fold Change})$ ($\log_2(FC)$) values obtained from Cuffdiff were directly used for gene expression profiling and co-expression analysis to assess relative expression changes under stress conditions.

Preparation and Normalisation of Gene Expression Data

Instead of using absolute expression levels (FPKM), $\log_2(FC)$ values were utilised to represent the relative gene expression changes under stress conditions compared to the control. The $\log_2(FC)$ values were derived from the ratio of treatment to control expression levels. In this dataset, positive values indicate upregulation, while negative values indicate downregulation of the gene under the specific

stress condition. These $\log_2(FC)$ values were subsequently used for heatmap construction and co-expression analysis to identify genes showing similar regulation patterns.

Co-expression-Based Identification of TFs and Kinases

To identify co-expression relationships, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated for each gene pair using $\log_2(FC)$ values. Gene pairs with a correlation coefficient of $r \geq 0.90$ were considered to be strongly co-expressed (Song et al., 2012).

A curated list of transcription factors (TFs) and kinases was retrieved from the iTAK database (Zheng et al., 2016), and these regulatory genes were matched against the co-expression results to identify TFs and kinases co-expressed with the *cysteine desulfurase* gene. P-values were not used as filters; instead, the stringent correlation threshold was employed to ensure high-confidence network construction.

Although *p*-values were not used to filter correlations, the high threshold of $r \geq 0.90$ was chosen to ensure the biological relevance of co-expression links and to reduce the risk of false positives. This approach aligns with previous co-expression studies (e.g., Song et al., 2012). Statistical significance values were not prioritised, as the primary objective was to construct a high-confidence interaction network rather than to test pairwise gene associations individually.

Annotation and Data Visualisation

The top upregulated and downregulated genes co-expressed with the *cysteine desulfurase* gene were annotated using the BioMart tool available in Ensembl Plants (Kinsella et al., 2011; Kersey et al., 2016). Gene-gene interactions, including transcription factors and kinases associated with the target gene, were visualised through correlation matrices and co-expression networks using Cytoscape software (Shannon et al., 2003).

Results

GO Annotation of Key Genes Interacting with *Cysteine Desulfurase*

Functional annotation of the top upregulated and downregulated genes co-expressed with the *cysteine desul-*

furase gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*) revealed their involvement in various biological processes, particularly those related to stress responses, cellular signalling, and metabolism (Table 1; Figure 2).

For example, *PGSC0003DMT400080385* is associated with cytochrome-c oxidase activity, proton transmembrane transport, and copper ion binding, indicating a role in mitochondrial respiration and oxidative stress defence. *PGSC0003DMT400065426*, encoding a putative membrane protein, showed strong expression under both drought and heat stress, suggesting involvement in membrane stability and transport.

Stress-responsive transcription factors were also prominent. *PGSC0003DMT400063264* (AP2/ERF family) and *PGSC0003DMT400056255* (MYB family) are known regulators of abiotic stress adaptation. Genes such as *PGSC0003DMT400006531* (a guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor) and *PGSC0003DMT400051014* (defence-related) point to signalling functions. Other genes were linked to mitochondrial and chloroplast processes, including *PGSC0003DMT400038370* (ubiquinone biosynthesis) and *PGSC0003DMT400023336* (regulation of the pentose phosphate cycle).

Genes involved in protein metabolism were also identified, such as *PGSC0003DMT400010044* and *PGSC0003DMT400039544*, which relate to protease activity and inhibition, respectively. Additionally, *PGSC0003DMT400052057* (a WRKY TF) was associated with phosphate ion transport and nuclear localisation.

Notably, *PGSC0003DMT400022675* and *PGSC0003DMT400023728* lacked functional annotation but showed significant expression changes under stress, suggesting potential novel regulatory roles that warrant further investigation.

Collectively, these co-expressed genes reflect a coordinated response involving transcriptional regulation, redox balance, membrane integrity, and metabolic adjustment. These insights strengthen the hypothesis that *cysteine desulfurase* acts as a regulatory hub under abiotic stress.

Expression of Key Genes Interacting with *Cysteine Desulfurase*

Expression profiles of the top genes co-expressed (Pearson $r > 0.90$) with the *cysteine desulfurase* gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*) were assessed under drought, heat, and salinity stress conditions.

Tabela 1. Gene Ontology-based functional annotation of the top upregulated and most downregulated genes interacting with *cysteine desulfurase*.

Table 1. Funkcionalna anotacija na podlagi genetske ontologije genov, ki interagirajo s *cisteinsko desulfurazo* z najbolj povečano in zmanjšano ekspresijo. genov.

Gene stable ID	Transcript stable ID	Function Summary
The most up-regulated genes		
PGSC0003DMG400002546	PGSC0003DMT400006531	Guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity, plasma membrane
PGSC0003DMG400021857	PGSC0003DMT400056255	MYB transcription factor
PGSC0003DMG400024606	PGSC0003DMT400063264	AP2/ERF transcription factor family
PGSC0003DMG401025438	PGSC0003DMT400065426	Membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG402014805	PGSC0003DMT400038370	Mitochondrion, protein-containing complex binding, ubiquinone biosynthesis
PGSC0003DMG400009042	PGSC0003DMT400023336	Chloroplast, negative regulation of the reductive pentose-phosphate cycle
PGSC0003DMG400019806	PGSC0003DMT400051014	Defense response
PGSC0003DMG401031302	PGSC0003DMT400080385	Cytochrome-c oxidase, proton transport, copper binding, membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG400028730	PGSC0003DMT400073927	Protein kinase activity
The most down-regulated genes		
PGSC0003DMG400009179	PGSC0003DMT400023728	Not annotated
PGSC0003DMG400015290	PGSC0003DMT400039544	Serine-type endopeptidase inhibitor activity
PGSC0003DMG400016970	PGSC0003DMT400043696	Membrane, phospholipid metabolic process
PGSC0003DMG402008792	PGSC0003DMT400022675	Not annotated
PGSC0003DMG400020206	PGSC0003DMT400052057	Transcription regulation, phosphate ion transport, and the nucleus
PGSC0003DMG400003044	PGSC0003DMT400007870	Thaumatococcus domain-containing protein
PGSC0003DMG402003937	PGSC0003DMT400010044	Proteolysis, serine-type endopeptidase activity
PGSC0003DMG400004549	PGSC0003DMT400011566	Membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG401025920	PGSC0003DMT400066701	Membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG400028369	PGSC0003DMT400072921	Nuclear transport factor

As shown in Figure 1 and summarised in Table 1, two genes—*PGSC0003DMT400065426* (membrane protein) and *PGSC0003DMT400080385* (cytochrome-c oxidase)—exhibited exceptionally high expression levels, particularly under heat and drought. *PGSC0003DMT400065426* reached a peak of $\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 28 under heat stress, while *PGSC0003DMT400080385* showed strong expression under both heat ($\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 27) and drought ($\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 24), suggesting putative *de novo* induction and critical roles in membrane stabilisation and mitochondrial function during stress adaptation.

In contrast, *PGSC0003DMT400022675* and *PGSC0003DMT400023728*, both unannotated, were

markedly downregulated under salinity and drought, as illustrated in Figure 2, implying their potential role in suppressing stress pathways.

Several genes showed significant expression ($\log_2(FC)$ value of 7–15) under heat stress, indicating selective activation in response to elevated temperature. These include: *PGSC0003DMT400038370* (ubiquinone biosynthesis in mitochondria), *PGSC0003DMT400023336* (negative regulator of the pentose-phosphate cycle in chloroplasts), and *PGSC0003DMT400056255* (MYB transcription factor).

Additionally, modest expression ($\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 3) was observed under both drought and salinity for several genes, including: *PGSC0003DMT400073927* (protein

kinase), *PGSC0003DMT400063264* (AP2/ERF TF), *PGSC0003DMT400006531* (guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor), and *PGSC0003DMT400051014* (defence-related gene), pointing to a modest but shared response mechanism.

Overall, these results highlight *PGSC0003DMT400065426* and *PGSC0003DMT400080385* as strong candidates for future functional validation studies, given their consistent and elevated expression under multiple abiotic stress conditions.

Co-expression Network of TFs and Kinases Interacting with *Cysteine Desulfurase*

To identify key regulatory components associated with *cysteine desulfurase* under stress, a co-expression network was constructed based on genes showing strong positive correlation ($r \geq 0.90$) with the target gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*). As shown in Figure 3, the resulting network comprises 202 nodes and 2,398 edges, representing highly co-expressed transcription factors (TFs) and kinases.

Annotation using the iTAK database classified the nodes into several regulatory families: 130 kinases, 10 MYB, 7 MYB-related, 12 bHLH, five bZIP, 7 C2H2, 3 C2C2-GATA, 6 NAC, 7 AP2/ERF-ERF, 2 AP2/ERF-AP2, 4 DOF, 3 HSF, 3 TCP, 1 SBP, and 1 Trihelix.

The central location of *cysteine desulfurase* in the network highlights its potential role as a regulatory hub, integrating both transcriptional and post-translational mechanisms. In particular, the presence of stress-related TF families such as AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bHLH—alongside a large number of kinases—suggests a coordinated network involving both gene expression modulation and phosphorylation signalling.

This integrated network underscores the multifunctional nature of *cysteine desulfurase* in stress response pathways and provides a basis for future functional validation of key TFs and kinases as potential regulators of abiotic stress tolerance in *Solanum tuberosum* (potato).

Discussion

Cysteine desulfurases (CDs) play pivotal roles in sulfur metabolism and the biosynthesis of cofactors such as *iron-sulfur (Fe-S) clusters* and *molybdenum cofactor*

(*Moco*), both of which are essential for redox regulation and metabolic stability under stress (Caubrière et al., 2023; Gotor et al., 2015). In this study, we analysed the co-expression profile of the predicted *cysteine desulfurase* gene *PGSC0003DMT400078713* in *Solanum tuberosum* under drought, heat, and salinity stress using RNA-Seq data. The results revealed 2,397 strongly co-expressed genes ($r \geq 0.90$), many of which are associated with transcriptional regulation, signalling pathways, redox balance, and membrane transport.

From these, 201 transcription factors and kinases were identified using the iTAK database. Notably, families such as AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bZIP were prevalent, all known to mediate abiotic stress responses (Romero et al., 2014; Tian et al., 2024). For example, *PGSC0003DMT400063264* (AP2/ERF) and *PGSC0003DMT400056255* (MYB) were co-expressed with the target gene, implying their involvement in regulating sulfur-related or oxidative stress responses, possibly via *H₂S* or *Fe-S cluster*-dependent signalling (Liu et al., 2024).

Among the top upregulated genes, *PGSC0003DMT400065426* (a membrane protein) and *PGSC0003DMT400080385* (*cytochrome-c oxidase*) showed increased expression under heat and drought stress, suggesting their roles in membrane transport and mitochondrial redox regulation (Yang et al., 2022). Their functions are consistent with the subcellular roles of *cysteine desulfurases* in mitochondria and chloroplasts (Caubrière et al., 2023), where *Fe-S clusters* are synthesised, and oxidative stress is managed.

Conversely, genes such as *PGSC0003DMT400023728* and *PGSC0003DMT400096412*, which lack functional annotation, were consistently downregulated under drought and salinity. Their suppression may reflect stress-induced inhibition of sulfur-rich metabolic pathways or shifts in redox balance due to disrupted *Fe-S* assembly or *H₂S* signalling (Vojtovič et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022).

GO analysis of co-expressed genes revealed enrichment in *proton transport*, *ubiquinone biosynthesis*, *proteolysis regulation*, and *intracellular signalling*. Of particular interest is *PGSC0003DMT400006531*, a guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor, which may link membrane signalling to sulfur metabolism via persulfidation or *H₂S*-mediated pathways (Aroca et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2024).

Taken together, the co-expression patterns of *PGSC0003DMT400078713* support its role as a central regulator in stress adaptation, likely coordinating transcrip-

Figure 1. The expression levels of the top co-expressed genes ($r > 0.9$) with cysteine desulfurase under drought, heat, and salinity conditions.
 Slika 1. Ravní izražanja najbolj soizraženih genov ($r > 0,9$) s cisteinsko desulfurazo v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti.

Figure 2. The expression levels of the most down-regulated genes ($r > 0.9$) co-expressed with cysteine desulfurase under drought, heat, and salinity conditions.
 Slika 2. Ravní izražanja najbolj navzdol reguliranih genov ($r > 0,9$), ki se soizražajo s cisteinsko desulfurazo v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti.

Figure 3. Co-expression network of transcription factors and kinases co-expressed with cysteine desulfurase in *Solanum tuberosum*. (A) The network includes 202 nodes and 2398 edges based on Pearson $r \geq 0.90$. (B) Nodes are colour-coded by gene family as classified using the iTAK database.

Slika 3. Mreža soizražanja transkripcijskih faktorjev in kinaz, ki se soizražajo s cisteinsko desulfurazo v *Solanum tuberosum*. (A) Mreža vključuje 202 vozlišča in 2398 robov na podlagi Pearsonovega $r \geq 0,90$. (B) Vozlišča so barvno označena po genih družinah, kot so razvrščene v bazi podatkov iTAK.

tional networks, redox signalling, and post-translational modifications under abiotic stress. These findings highlight the multifunctional nature of *cysteine desulfurases* and provide a foundation for future research into targeted stress resilience strategies in potato.

Conclusion

This study investigated the gene networks involving *cysteine desulfurases* in *Solanum tuberosum* under abiotic stress, with a particular focus on transcription factors (TFs) and kinases co-expressed with the gene *PGSC0003DMT400078713* during drought, heat, and salinity exposure. Through co-expression analysis of RNA-Seq data, combined with functional annotation and network visualisation, 2,397 genes were identified as strongly correlated ($r \geq 0.90$) with the target gene. Among these, 201 TFs and kinases belonged to well-known stress-responsive families such as AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bHLH, reflecting a coordinated regulatory network involving both transcriptional and post-translational mechanisms.

Notably, a membrane-associated protein (*PGSC0003DMT400065426*) and a *cytochrome-c oxidase* (*PGSC0003DMT400080385*) involved in redox regulation and mitochondrial respiration were strongly upregulated under heat and drought, suggesting their functional role in redox homeostasis and energy metabolism. In contrast, uncharacterized genes such as *PGSC0003DMT400096412* and *PGSC0003DMT400022675* were consistently downregulated under salinity and drought, indicating possible involvement in suppressed or stress-inhibited pathways.

Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment highlighted processes such as *oxidative stress response*, *signal transduction*, *proteolysis regulation*, and *subcellular localisation*, further supporting the biological diversity of the genes co-expressed with *cysteine desulfurase*.

Together, these findings enhance our understanding of the molecular networks governing abiotic stress tolerance in *potato* and underscore the central role of *cysteine desulfurases* in *sulfur metabolism* and *redox signalling*. The identified candidate genes provide a basis for future functional validation and genetic improvement strategies aimed at enhancing stress resilience in *potato* cultivars.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, F.K.; methodology, F.K.; software, F.K.; validation, F.K. and E.F.; formal analysis, F.K.; investigation, F.K.; resources, E.F.; data curation, E.F.; writing—original draft preparation, F.K.; writing—review and editing, F.K. and E.F.; visualization, F.K.; supervision, E.F.; project administration, F.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Recep Vatansver for providing the processed RNA-seq dataset and for his assistance regarding the details of the bioinformatic analysis

Funding

This research received no external funding

Data Availability

RNA-Seq expression data generated by the Potato Genome Sequencing Consortium (PGSC) for the reference genotype DM1-3 were downloaded from the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession SRA029323, associated with BioProject PRJEB2430. The research data generated during the current study and used for the analyses are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17798426>.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

- Afgan, E., Baker, D., van den Beek, M., Blankenberg, D., Bouvier, D., Čech, M., ... Goecks, J. (2016). The Galaxy platform for accessible, reproducible and collaborative biomedical analyses: 2016 update. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(W1), W3–W10. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw343>
- Aroca, A., Gotor, C., Bassham, D. C., & Romero, L. C. (2020). Hydrogen sulfide: From a toxic molecule to a key molecule of cell life. *Antioxidants*, 9(7), 621. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9070621>
- Caubrière, D., Moseler, A., Rouhier, N., & Couturier, J. (2023). Diversity and roles of cysteine desulfurases in photosynthetic organisms. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 74(11), 3345–3360. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erad065>
- Das, R. R., Pradhan, S., & Parida, A. (2020). De-novo transcriptome analysis unveils differentially expressed genes regulating drought and salt stress response in *Panicum sumatrense*. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 78118. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78118-3>
- Edgar, R., Domrachev, M., & Lash, A. E. (2002). Gene Expression Omnibus: NCBI gene expression and hybridization array data repository. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 30(1), 207–210. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/30.1.207>
- Gotor, C., Laureano-Marín, A. M., Moreno, I., Aroca, Á., García, I., & Romero, L. C. (2015). Signaling in the plant cytosol: Cysteine or sulfide? *Amino Acids*, 47(10), 2155–2164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-014-1786-z>
- Heis, M. D., Dítter, E. M., de Oliveira, L. A., Frazzon, A. P. G., Margis, R., & Frazzon, J. (2011). Differential expression of cysteine desulfurases in soybean. *BMC Plant Biology*, 11, 166. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2229-11-166>
- Jia, H., Wang, X., Dou, Y., Liu, D., Si, W., Fang, H., Zhao, C., Chen, S., Xi, J., & Li, J. (2016). Hydrogen sulfide-cysteine cycle system enhances cadmium tolerance through alleviating cadmium-induced oxidative stress and ion toxicity in *Arabidopsis* roots. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 39702. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep39702>
- Jin, Z., Sun, L., Yang, G., & Pei, Y. (2018). Hydrogen sulfide regulates energy production to delay leaf senescence induced by drought stress in *Arabidopsis*. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9, 1722. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01722>
- Kersey, P. J., Allen, J. E., Armean, I., Boddu, S., Bolt, B. J., Carvalho-Silva, D., Christensen, M., Davis, P., Falin, L. J., Grabmueller, C., Humphrey, J., Kerhornou, A., Khobova, J., Aranganathan, N. K., Langridge, N., Lowy, E., McDowall, M. D., Maheswari, U., Nuhn, M., ... Staines, D. M. (2016). Ensembl Genomes 2016: More genomes, more complexity. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(D1), D574–D580. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1209>
- Khan, M. S. S., Islam, F., Ye, Y., Ashline, M., Wang, D., Zhao, B., Fu, Z. Q., & Chen, J. (2022). The interplay between hydrogen sulfide and phytohormone signaling pathways under challenging environments. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(8), 4272. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23084272>
- Kinsella, R. J., Kähäri, A., Haider, S., Zamora, J., Proctor, G., Spudich, G., Almeida-King, J., Staines, D., Derwent, P., Kerhornou, A., Kersey, P., & Flicek, P. (2011). Ensembl BioMarts: A hub for data retrieval across taxonomic space. *Database: The Journal of Biological Databases and Curation*, 2011, bar030. <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/bar030>
- Langmead, B., Trapnell, C., Pop, M., & Salzberg, S. L. (2009). Ultrafast and memory-efficient alignment of short DNA sequences to the human genome. *Genome Biology*, 10(3), R25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/gb-2009-10-3-r25>
- Li, Q., Qin, Y., Hu, X., Li, G., Ding, H., Xiong, X., & Wang, W. (2020). Transcriptome analysis uncovers the gene expression profile of salt-stressed potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 62057. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-62057-0>
- Liu, H., & Xue, S. (2021). Interplay between hydrogen sulfide and other signaling molecules in the regulation of guard cell signaling and abiotic/biotic stress response. *Plant Communications*, 2(3), 100179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xplc.2021.100179>
- Liu, M., Li, Y., Li, G., Dong, T., Liu, S., Liu, P., & Wang, G. Q. (2020). Overexpression of *StCYS1* gene enhances tolerance to salt stress in the transgenic potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) plant. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, 19(9), 2239–2246. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119\(20\)63262-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119(20)63262-2)
- Liu, Z., Liu, Y., & Liao, W. (2024). Hydrogen sulfide in the oxidative stress response of plants: Crosstalk with reactive oxygen species. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 25(3), 1935. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25031935>
- Nicolas, M., Bouma, J., Venema, J. H., van der Schoot, H., Verstappen, F., de Zeeuw, T., Langedijk, S. E., Boer, D., Bucher, J., Staal, M., Krom, B., Elzenga, J. T. M., Visser, R. G. F., Testerink, C., & Karlova, R. (2025). Potato cultivars use distinct mechanisms for salt stress acclimation. *Plant Stress*, 15, 100798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stress.2025.100798>
- Massa, A. N., Childs, K. L., Lin, H., Bryan, G. J., Giuliano, G., & Buell, C. R. (2011). The transcriptome of the reference potato genome *Solanum tuberosum* Group Phureja clone DM1-3 516R44. *PLoS One*, 6(10), e26801. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0026801>
- Pandey, A. K., & Gautam, A. (2020). Stress responsive gene regulation in relation to hydrogen sulfide in plants under abiotic stress. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 168(2), 511–525. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppl.13064>
- Romero, L. C., Aroca, M. Á., Laureano-Marín, A. M., Moreno, I., García, I., & Gotor, C. (2014). Cysteine and cysteine-related signaling pathways in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Molecular Plant*, 7(2), 264–276. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mp/sst168>
- Shannon, P., Markiel, A., Ozier, O., Baliga, N. S., Wang, J. T., Ramage, D., ... Ideker, T. (2003). Cytoscape: A software environment for integrated models of biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Research*, 13(11), 2498–2504. <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.1239303>
- Song, L., Langfelder, P., & Horvath, S. (2012). Comparison of co-expression measures: Mutual information, correlation, and model-based indices. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 13, 328. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-13-328>
- Tang, Q., Zhou, Y., Zhou, D., Hong, J., Zhao, L., Bu, G., Chen, F., & Tang, L. (2023). The ethylene response factor RAP2.6 plays a positive role in the regulation of selenium tolerance in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 99(2), 241–250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10725-022-00901-1>
- Tian, T., Zhu, J., Li, Z., Wang, W., Bao, M., Qiu, X., Yao, P., Bi, Z., Sun, C., Li, Y., Liu, Z., & Liu, Y. (2024). Comprehensive analysis of the OASTL gene family in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) and its expression under abiotic stress. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 25(23), 13170. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms252313170>

- Trapnell, C., Pachter, L., & Salzberg, S. L. (2009). TopHat: Discovering splice junctions with RNA-Seq. *Bioinformatics*, 25(9), 1105–1111. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp120>
- Trapnell, C., Williams, B. A., Pertea, G., Mortazavi, A., Kwan, G., van Baren, M. J., ... Pachter, L. (2010). Transcript assembly and quantification by RNA-Seq reveals unannotated transcripts and isoform switching during cell differentiation. *Nature Biotechnology*, 28(5), 511–515. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.1621>
- Trapnell, C., Roberts, A., Goff, L., Pertea, G., Kim, D., Kelley, D. R., Pimentel, H., Salzberg, S. L., Rinn, J. L., & Pachter, L. (2012). Differential gene and transcript expression analysis of RNA-seq experiments with TopHat and Cufflinks. *Nature Protocols*, 7(3), 562–578. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2012.016>
- Vojtovič, D., Luhová, L., & Petřivalský, M. (2021). Something smells bad to plant pathogens: Production of hydrogen sulfide in plants and its role in plant defence responses. *Journal of Advanced Research*, 27, 199–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2020.09.005>
- Xu, X., Pan, S., Cheng, S., Zhang, B., Mu, D., Ni, P., ... Visser, R. G. F. (2011). Genome sequence and analysis of the tuber crop potato. *Nature*, 475, 189–195. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10158>
- Yang, Z., Wang, X., Feng, J., & Zhu, S. (2022). Biological functions of hydrogen sulfide in plants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(23), 15107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232315107>
- Zheng, Y., Jiao, C., Sun, H., Rosli, H. G., Pombo, M. A., Zhang, P., ... Fei, Z. (2016). iTAK: A program for genome-wide prediction and classification of plant transcription factors, transcriptional regulators, and protein kinases. *Molecular Plant*, 9(12), 1667–1670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molp.2016.09.014>